

Nitrogen Mustards. Part III

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Attempts to prepare nitrogen mustard intermediates by the Mannich reaction from 2- and 4-methylpyridines, formaldehyde, and diethanolamine have failed. The structure of the product of this reaction is discussed. 2-Picoyl chloride condenses easily with diethanolamine and a nitrogen mustard intermediate has thus been obtained.

The Mannich reaction was reported to take place with the reactive hydrogen of the methyl group at 2- or 4-position in pyridine and quinoline and thus several primary and secondary amines were condensed¹⁻² with the above bases in presence of formaldehyde. This led us to investigate a new route for the preparation of nitrogen mustard intermediates of types (I) and (II) by the condensation of diethanolamine hydrochloride and formaldehyde in the Mannich type reaction with the hydrogen of a methyl group at 2- or 4-position in pyridine. The attempted condensation of diethanolamine(III), formaldehyde, and 2- or 4-methylpyridine or their *N*-oxides under a variety of conditions, however, failed to furnish the desired product. In every case the product appeared to be the same, a liquid boiling at 106-107°/8 mm. It was soluble in water and organic solvents and failed to provide a picrate or hydrochloride. The UV spectra of this liquid indicated absence of pyridine ring.

The oil obtained from each reaction was found to undergo benzylation and the liquid esters, thus obtained, afforded a solid hydrochloride, m.p. 135-36°, and also a picrate, m.p. 140-41.5°. The liquids, obtained in each case, were thus found identical. This led us to conclude that formaldehyde and diethanolamine must have condensed together to provide (VI) which on benzylation would furnish (VII). The analytical data obtained for the hydrochloride of (VII) suggest the original liquid to be of structure (VI). That condensations of this type between formaldehyde and secondary amines do occur in the Mannich reactions are known and measures to prevent it have been suggested³.

1. "Organic Reactions", Vol. I, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1947, p. 312.
2. Levy and Nisbet, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1063.
3. Israel *et al.*, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, 48, 1940.

[IX: R=CH₂, CH₂OH; R₁=H].

[X: R=R₁=CH₂, CH₂OH].

[XI: R=R₁=CH₂, CH₂OOC.Ph].

The structure of compound (VI) was then confirmed by synthesising it by refluxing formaldehyde and diethanolamine (III) in acetic acid. Product (VI), on benzylation yielded (VII) which was characterised as its hydrochloride. Further, when the di-ester (IV) was refluxed with formaldehyde in acetic acid solution and the product treated with dry hydrogen chloride, the final compound was found to be identical with the hydrochloride of (VII). It is thus evident that the hydroxyl groups of (III) are not involved in any way in the condensation of formaldehyde and (III), and that the product may have structure (VI) only. The above facts confirm that the Mannich reaction completely fails and only a simple condensation of the aldehyde with two moles of (III) takes place. Condensation of benzaldehyde with (III) provided an oil (characterised through its picrate), probably possessing structure (VIII).

Preparation of nitrogen mustard intermediates of types (IX) and (X) by the reaction of 2-chloromethylpyridine with ethanolamine and diethanolamine (III) was then investigated. The reaction between (III) and 2-picoyl chloride hydrochloride proceeded smoothly affording product (X) in good yield. This was benzyolated easily to yield (XI), isolated as its hydrochloride. The UV spectra indicated presence of the pyridine ring in (X). Further more, the properties of (X), its high solubility in water and high boiling point are in full accord with the structure assigned.

Compound (IV) as its hydrochloride was prepared by Schotten-Baumann reaction between (III) and benzoyl chloride according to the method of Gabali and Zeid⁴. Our product, however, had a higher melting point. According to them⁴ the di-ester amide (V) is known and they have cited the work of Brintzinger and Koddebusch⁵. These workers⁵ did not, however, describe (V) although a mention was made. We find that the di-ester amide (V) is easily obtained from (III) in good yield if considerable excess of benzoyl chloride is used and after vigorous shaking the mixture is allowed to stand for a few hours. This compound is also obtained in a low yield with a smaller proportion of benzoyl chloride provided that the mixture after shaking is allowed to stand overnight.

The IR spectrum of the hydrochloride of (IV) shows bands at 2418 (w), 2485 (s), and 2855(s) cm⁻¹, indicating presence of secondary amine hydrochloride. The characteristic band for the hydroxyl group is absent. It therefore appears that in the benzyolation of (III), the two hydroxyl groups are first converted into the ester group, leading to the di-ester (IV), followed by a slow attack on the secondary nitrogen. Thus, the secondary nitrogen of (III) is less reactive than the hydroxyl groups, a fact in accord with the observation of previous workers⁴⁻⁶. The recent results of Rigamonty *et al.*⁷, however, appears quite different and we fail to confirm it.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2076.

5. *Ber.*, 1949, 82, 201.

6. Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 461.

7. *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 60, 5297c.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Di-(β-benzoyloxyethyl)amine Hydrochloride (IV).—Freshly distilled diethanolamine (1*M*, 5.25 g.) was taken in a conical flask and excess of 10% NaOH solution was added. Benzoyl chloride (2*M*, 14.05 g.) was poured in the mixture which was vigorously shaken till there was no odour of the acid chloride. The flask was frequently cooled under tap. The benzoyl ester separating as an oil was extracted with ether, washed, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Dry hydrogen chloride gas was then passed through the ethereal solution and white crystals (4 g.) of the hydrochloride separating on cooling, were crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture as white feathery crystals, m.p. 160-62° (lit.⁴ reports m.p. 138-40°). (Found: N, 4.18; Cl, 9.46. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{NCl}$ requires N, 4.00; Cl, 10.04%). The IR spectrum was recorded in nujol mull on a Perkin Elmer Infracord.

NN-Bis-(β-benzoyloxyethyl)benzamide (V).—Freshly distilled diethanolamine (1*M*, 5.25 g.) was mixed with an excess of 10% NaOH solution and to this was added purified benzoyl chloride (4*M*, 28.1 g.). The mixture was vigorously shaken for sometimes when an oil separated; it was then allowed to stand for 10-12 hr. The oil solidified to a white mass. This was powdered, filtered, and washed to provide a white substance (16 g.) which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in white hexagonal plates, m.p. 70-71.5°. (Found: N, 3.72. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires N, 3.35%).

Di-[bis-(β-hydroxyethyl)aminomethane (VI)].—A mixture of freshly distilled diethanolamine (31.5 g.), excess paraformaldehyde (9 g.), and acetic acid (300 ml) was refluxed for 38 hr. Acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure from the brown reaction mixture and the residue was basified with potassium carbonate. It was then repeatedly extracted with chloroform. The combined extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed; the residual brown liquid was distilled under reduced pressure when a colorless, and odorless basic fraction was obtained (21 g.), b.p. 106-107°/8 mm. (Found: C, 49.10; H, 9.82. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 48.64; H, 9.92%).

Di-[bis-(β-benzoyloxyethyl)] aminomethane (VI)

Method (A).—Compound (VI) (2.2 g.), dissolved in excess of 10% aqueous NaOH solution, was treated with excess of purified benzoyl chloride. An oil separating was extracted with ether, washed, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the ether furnished a viscous oil which was not distilled. The dihydrochloride was obtained by passing dry HCl gas through the ethereal solution of this oil which on cooling deposited white crystals. These were purified by crystallisation from ethanol-ether mixture, m.p. 135-30°. (Found: N, 4.33; Cl, 10.19. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 3.93; Cl, 10.00%).

The *picrate* was obtained from both ethanolic and methanolic solutions in good yields and was crystallised from ethanol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 140-41.5°. (Found: C, 54.29; H, 4.57. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2$. $2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires C, 53.80; H, 4.02%).

Method (B).—A mixture of the hydrochloride of the di-ester (IV) (1*M*, 6.99 g.), excess of formaldehyde solution (5 ml, 40%), and acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 22 hr. The mixture turned brown from which acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure. The residual deep brown viscous oil was extracted several times with ether. The residue was then dissolved in the minimum amount of water, basified with potassium carbonate,

* All melting points are uncorrected.

and repeatedly extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of the ether, a yellow oil was obtained (4 g.) which was dissolved in dry ether; dry HCl gas was passed into the solution when crystals of the hydrochloride separated on cooling. These were recrystallised from ethanol-ether mixture, m.p. 134-36°. Mixed m.p. with the compound obtained by method (A) was 135-36°.

The *picrate* was obtained from ethanolic solution in good yield, m.p. 139-41°. Mixed m.p. with the *picrate* of the compound obtained by method (A) was 138-41°.

Phenyl-di-[bis-(β-hydroxyethyl)amino]methane (VIII).—Freshly distilled benzaldehyde (1*M*, 10.6 g.) and diethanolamine (2*M*, 21.0 g.) were added to acetic acid (40 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 48 hr. Acetic acid and unchanged benzaldehyde were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with aqueous paste of potassium carbonate and extracted repeatedly with ether. The ether extracts were combined, washed, and dried (Na_2SO_4). On removing the ether, a viscous yellow oil (9.5 g.) remained. It distilled at about 160-67°/8 mm (8 g.). The oil is insoluble in water.

The *picrate* was prepared from ethanolic solution and crystallised from ethanol in glistening yellow needles, m.p. 232° (with previous darkening at 228°). (Found: C, 41.68; H, 5.17. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_2\text{N}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 41.80; H, 4.40%.)

2-[(β-Hydroxyethyl)aminomethyl]pyridine (IX).—A mixture of 2-picoly chloride hydrochloride⁸⁻⁹ (1*M*, 3.28 g.), ethanolamine (1.22 g., excess), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1*M*, 2.76 g.) was refluxed in pure and dry isopropanol (25 ml) for 24 hr. The reddish reaction mixture was filtered hot and the solid washed with dry chloroform. The combined filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was distilled under reduced pressure, providing a light yellow liquid (2 g.), b.p. 150-55°/6.5 mm.

The *picrate* of the base was easily obtained in good yield from ethanolic solution as shining, yellow, feathery crystals, m.p. 152-54°. (Found: C, 41.16; H, 4.28. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_2\text{N}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O})$ requires C, 41.18; H, 4.41%.)

2-[Di-(β hydroxyethyl)aminomethyl]pyridine (X).—A mixture of 2-picoly chloride hydrochloride (8.2 g.) and diethanolamine (7.25 g., excess) was refluxed in dry and purified isopropanol (50 ml) for 50 hr. The dark brown reaction mixture was cooled and the isopropanol was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was basified with K_2CO_3 , extracted with chloroform (200 ml), and the extract dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residual oil was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure; b.p. 187-90°/3.5 mm (3 g.).

The *hydrochloride* was prepared by passing dry HCl in an ethanolic solution of the base with cooling. It separated as shining white needles and was crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture, m.p. 164-66°. (Found: N, 10.71; Cl, 26.33. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 10.41; Cl, 26.4%). λ_{max} 228, 250, 282 μ .

2-[Di-(β benzoyloxyethyl)aminomethyl]pyridine (XI).—The hydrochloride of compound (X) (1.5 g.) was dissolved in a little water and treated with a slight excess of 10% NaOH solution, when the solution turned dull red. It was vigorously shaken with ex-

8. Bookelheide and Linn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1286.

9. Winterfeld and Flick, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1937, 51, 11346d.

cess of benzoyl chloride with cooling. A highly sticky, deep brown oil separating was extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). Dry HCl gas was passed through the dry ethereal solution and a brown oil separating gradually solidified to a white mass on cooling. This was filtered and washed with dry ether (yield 2 g). It was recrystallised from ethanol-ether mixture in well-defined shining white needles, m.p. 165.5° . (Found: N, 6.07. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 5.87%).

The *picrate* was prepared in good yield in ethanol; m.p. $150-51^\circ$. (Found: C, 58.27; H, 4.77. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires, C, 56.90; H, 4.27%).

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